

A new remote laboratory of a pumping system designed using a low-cost hardware model

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Abstract

Automatics and Control subjects are always improved when the classroom teaching is supported by adequate laboratory experiments in order to provide students a deep understanding of theoretical lessons. However, both expensive equipment and limited time prevent teachers from having enough educational platforms. Thus, several low cost and flexible solutions have been developed to permit an effective teaching in Automatics and Control at a reasonable cost. Virtual and remote laboratories are inside this group of solutions as Web-based experimentation tools which have demonstrated the importance and effectiveness of hand-on experiences. This paper presents a new remote laboratory of a pumping system. The developed application allows students to remotely practice different theoretical concepts on the industrial process, which has been designed using a low-cost hardware model. In this paper, the most important features of the remote laboratory are described. The application proposes a set of practical experiences which students must resolve making use of the remote laboratory.

Keywords: Automation, e-learning, PLC programming, remote laboratory.

1 Introduction

Experimentation is one of the most important issues for engineering students, not only because it allows them to observe and explore real-world applications but also because it helps to develop a deep understanding of theoretical lessons. The subjects of Automation and Control require experimentation with real equipment as, for example, the PLC (Programmable Logic Controller).

One of the guidelines determined by ESHE (European Space of Higher Education) is that traditional education must be combined with distance education, because a good distance teaching education provides flexibility to students. In this new educational context, and in the field of Automatics and Control education, virtual and remote laboratories play an important role because they are designed for an independent learner and/or a distance self-learning (Heradio et al., 2016). In the case of remote labs, these allow students to practice with real physical equipment located in remote places being accessible at any time and place with an Internet connection.

In Automatics and Control teaching, there are several low-cost remote laboratories via the Internet that facilitates the development of new educational methodologies in this field (Domínguez et. al., 2005). For example, different remote-control laboratories for conducting teaching practices through the Internet were presented in (Costa-Castelló et. al., 2010). Other remote laboratory based on very low-cost devices is presented in (Kalúz et. al., 2014). In this case, a remote laboratory for control education was developed using Raspberry and Arduino. In addition, several approaches have developed remote laboratories which allow real experimentation of hardware models that emulates real systems. This is the case of the works presented in (Kalúz et. al., 2014; Angulo & García-Zubía, 2014), where a quadruple tank process and a three floors elevator were implemented with real industrial equipment. In this field, other approaches about remote labs have been developed for control of industrial processes (Domínguez et. al., 2014; Prada et. al., 2015; Del Canto et. al. 2015; Aydogmus & Aydogmus, 2009).

The work presented in this paper shows the successful application of a new remote laboratory used in the practical learning of the subjects "Automatic Control Systems" and "Automatics and Robotics" taught in the

Automatics and Robotics Master's Degree, and in the Computer Science Degree, both at the University of Alicante. The application allows students to remotely practice different theoretical concepts using the hardware model of a real industrial process (pumping system). The industrial process has been designed and implemented by a low-cost hardware model. Students remotely program the main controller of the plant and can visualize the results obtained via a web interface and video streaming feedback.

2 Remote laboratory description

2.1 Pumping process emulated by the remote laboratory

The aim of the controller of a real pumping system is to keep stable a pressure value in an industrial plant. For that end, one of the pumps must be controlled by an inverter with the output frequency needed to achieve the reference pressure value. When the water demand cannot be achieved with only one pump controlled by the inverter, one or more of the remaining pumps can be directly connected to the three-phase power line connection by means of contactors managed by the controller. In the case of an increase of the pressure (decrease in demand) pumps must be disconnected from the three-phase line. If there is not demand, the pump controlled by the inverter will be also disconnected. Furthermore, the system must control that all the pumps have the same use over time.

The hardware devices of the remote laboratory emulate a real case of a pumping station. Specifically, the real device emulated is the typical water distribution system of an industrial plant. In this case, the pumping system has 4 pumps and only one inverter. The controller of the pumping system must be able to adapt the system to any water demand using the 4 pumps and the inverter. For this purpose, a pressure sensor is connected to the main controller in order to give a pressure value of the distributed water (in a range of 0-10 bars, traduced to 4-20mA).

2.2 Hardware model of the remote lab

The hardware model of the pumping system is shown in Figure 1. It shows the following components:

- A three-phase motor of 4 magnetic poles.
- An inverter MX2 connected to the motor.
- A PLC type CP1L-J from OMRON.
- An HMI (Human Machine Interface) screen to monitor the hardware.
- Several output lights for the simulation of the state of the pumps.
- An Ethernet switch for the network connection.

As commented, this hardware model emulates a real pumping system of 4 pumps, which is in charge of maintaining a stable pressure of 6 bars regardless of the demand. The main controller of the industrial system is the CP1L, whose digital outputs are employed to indicate the pump controlled by the inverter MX2 (only one pump can be controlled at the same time) and to indicate the active pumps directly connected to the three-phase line (at 100% of their power). The three-phase motor represents the pump controlled by the inverter, which must send to the motor a correct frequency to maintain the pressure and to adjust the demand.

The CJ1 is in charge of simulating the industrial plant. This device runs a program in order to analyse the signals coming from the CP1L, such as the pump controlled by the inverter and the active pumps. An analog input of the CJ1 is used to read the speed of the motor controlled by the inverter.

The program of this last equipment produces as a result the calculated for the simulated pressure sensor (controlled and active pumps). This value of the transducer is sent through an analog signal directly to the MX2 inverter, so it is possible to use it as feedback input for the inverter PID controller. In addition, the CJ1 can load different profiles of water demand where the value of the demand changes in real time. These profiles of the demand are used as practical experiences for the students.

2.3 The remote laboratory

The hardware model presented has been implemented as a remote laboratory. Different software and hardware elements have been added in order to provide remote functionalities to students. Figure 3 shows the connections between the devices of the hardware model and the Internet.

Remote capabilities allow students to load their programs to the CP1L by means of the software of the PLC's manufacturer, connecting to a specific IP of the PLC. The router of the hardware architecture of the remote laboratory performs a NAT (Network Address Translation) for programming the PLC as a local IP using the cloud. The CJ1 is connected through Ethernet to a web server (see Figure 3). Through this connection, the server can send commands that modify certain memory parameters in the CP1L. The main purpose of this functionality is to generate a few demand/time profiles in the plant.

Figure 1. Hardware model of the pumping system

At the same time, through this connection, the web server monitors the status of the simulated plant: state of the pumps connected to the inverter, state of the pumps connected to the three-phase line, pumps in error state, demand, pressure transducer and motor speed (which simulate the controlled pump speed). This information is used to update a SCADA interface, which is shown to students, so they can follow the evolution of the plant under the control program loaded (see Figure 2). In addition, the server reflects the evolution in time of the different parameters of the given profile and generates several graphs that will be sent to the students. Then, students can analyse the response of their programs and fix the errors found in the response. The web server also performs a video-streaming feedback of the real plant in order to provide students a real state of the emulated pumping system (see Client Interface in Figure 3).

In terms of hardware and software description, the web server has been developed by low-cost hardware, specifically with a Raspberry Pi 3 and the camera Module V2. The communication between the web server and the plant (PLCs CP1L and CJ1) is performed by the Modbus protocol. SCADA interface has been developed in different languages such as C#, JavaScript, CSS and HTML. It also makes use of tools and libraries such as Entity Framework, MEF (Managed Extensibility Framework), AngularJS and SQL Server.

For a correct access of students to the remote plant, there are two critical services within the server: access restricted to registered students (with username and password) and a booking system, so that only one user

can try to load the program and try to do the exercises. This booking system is a program that assigns a schedule (day and time) so the student can enter the system remotely through the Internet and perform the practical exercises.

Figure 2. SCADA interface

Figure 3. Remote laboratory description

3 Practical experiences

Practical experiences deal with different profiles of water demand for the pumping system. Students must program the main controller of the plant (CP1L) in order to perform a correct management of both the pumps and the inverter. In this section, a practical exercise of the remote plant is described.

Figure 4 shows a demand profile from the practical exercises of the students. This introduces an ascending ramp followed by a descending ramp and checks the output pressure of about 6 bars which must keep stable in the system.

Figure 4. Practical exercise of the remote lab

The initial demand of the system is zero. This demand will progressively increase until 78m³/h. Once this demand is achieved, this value is maintained for 30 seconds and subsequently decreases until zero. The proposed system uses a PID controller in the MX2 inverter in order to assure a pressure of 6 bars during all the experiment. At the beginning of the experiment, the system connects the first pump when the demand begins (pump 1 in the example). This first pump will be the one controlled by the PID of the inverter in order to allow the system to regulate the pressure (Figure 5).

Figure 5. SCADA visualization and video feedback of the web environment (I)

After some time, the same thing will occur, i.e., the controlled pump has an output frequency of 50 Hz. Therefore, a new pump (pump 3) must be connected to the three-phase network (Figure 6). As previously indicated, after 27 seconds, the demand begins to decrease. When the frequency is 0 Hz during several seconds, the program implemented by the student must detect that an over-pressure is generated. Therefore, the program must progressively deactivate the pumps connected to the three-phase network. The pumps must be deactivated considering the time used in each other in order to equalize the use of the pumps.

This situation will continue until all the pumps connected to the three-phase network are deactivated. Finally, the demand decreases until the controlled pump must be also deactivated, by stopping the inverter first and then deactivating the pump. Therefore, the student must develop a program in the CP1L with these points in order to perform a correct behaviour of the industrial system.

Figure 6. SCADA visualization and video feedback of the web environment (II)

4 Teaching framework

This approach is being used in the following courses with contents about industrial processes and automation: Automation and Robotics in the Computer Science Engineering Degree, and Automatic Control Systems in the Automatics and Robotics Master's Degree. In both, there are some didactic units about automation and control, where the main learning objectives are:

- To explain sensors and actuators employed in the industrial systems.
- To explain the PLC device and its operation principles.
- To teach how to use the PLC to control industrial processes.
- To explain how to program the PLC based on IEC1131-3 norm.
- To explain basic concepts about classic control theory such as PID controllers.

This application proposed has been integrated a blended learning educational methodology. Students, in the assistant classes perform the configuration of the MX2 inverter (first tasks). Afterwards, they can program the

PLC using the remote laboratory and the assistant classes. The main objective to reach by the remote laboratory is that students can implement, monitor and verify control and automation techniques from home as if they were in the industrial plant. This overall objective is specified in the following items:

- To have a hardware platform with similar features to those existing in an industrial environment. This way, students can practice concepts such as: adjustment of PID controllers, programming of PLCs, industrial communications and adjustment of inverter's parameters.
- To provide students a remote access to this hardware platform in order to perform experiments from home. The remote laboratory must be an environment for self-learning. For this objective, the system detects possible errors and offers the necessary feedback to the user.
- To have a self-assessment system. The system automatically establishes different operating modes or practical experiences to evaluate all the cases that may occur in a real industrial system.

This laboratory, with the features above commented, provides an improvement in the learning process of the student to be this active, self-directed, and constructive. The practical experiments proposed aim to evaluate the following concepts of operation in students about a real pumping industrial system:

- The suitable power on/off of the pumps and their time of operation.
- The adjustment of the frequency of the inverter and the PID controller.
- The communication task between the PLCs and the inverter.

5 Students' opinion

Most of the students consider this remote laboratory an efficient tool in the learning process that encourages their ability to understand control and automation concepts. In addition, they can experiment with real hand-on practices from their home as in the real laboratory, with a flexible timetable and providing more opportunities to try the response of their programs. Thus, this remote lab has improved student learning outcomes in terms of practical experiences.

Another question asked to the students was about the software to be installed, and the ease of use of the remote laboratory. None of the students had problems with the installation of the necessary software programs and they were able to adapt quickly to the user interfaces.

6 Conclusion

A new remote laboratory employed in the practical learning of the subjects "Automatic Control Systems" and "Automation and Robotics" taught in the Automatics and Robotics Master's Degree, and Computer Science Degree both at the University of Alicante, has been described. The presented application allows students to remotely practice different theoretical concepts using a hardware model of a real industrial process about a pumping system. The use of the proposed tool allows reinforcing students' active learning since they can perform practical exercises with the aim of understanding the acquired knowledge. In addition, students can understand the scope of theoretical concepts by applying them to a realistic industrial environment. As future work, authors are working in several aspects of the remote lab such as improving interfaces and model, and providing more practical exercises.

7 References

- Angulo, I., & García-Zubía, J. (2014). Experimentación Remota sobre Maqueta Industrial Basada en un Ascensor de Tres Plantas. *IEEE Versión Abierta Español-Portugués*, 2(4), 199-204.
- Aydogmus Z., & Aydogmus, O. (2009). A Web-Based Remote Access Laboratory Using SCADA". *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 52(1), 126-132.
- Costa-Castelló, R., Vallés, M., Jiménez, L.M., Díaz-Guerra, L., Valera, A., & Puerto, R. (2010). Integración de dispositivos físicos en un laboratorio remoto de control mediante diferentes plataformas: Labview, Matlab y C/C++. *Revista Iberoamericana de Automática e Informática Industrial*, 7(1), 23-24.
- Del Canto, Carlos J., Prada, Miguel A., Fuertes, Juan J., Alonso S., & Domínguez M. (2015). Remote Laboratory for Cybersecurity of Industrial Control Systems. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 48(29), 13-18.

- Domínguez, M., Reguera, P., & Fuertes, J.J. (2005). Laboratorio remoto para la enseñanza de la automática en la universidad de León". *Revista Iberoamericana de Automática e Informática Industrial*, 2(2), 36-45.
- Domínguez, M., Fuertes, J.J., Prada, M. A., Alonso, S., & Morán, A. (2014). Remote Laboratory of a Quadruple Tank Process for Learning in Control Engineering Using Different Industrial Controllers. *Computer Applications in Engineering Education*, 22(3), 375-386.
- Heradio, R., de la Torre, L. & Dormido, S. (2016). Virtual and remote labs in control education: A survey. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 42, 1-10.
- Kalúz, Martin, Cirka, L'ubos, Valo, Richard, & Fikar, Miroslav. (2014). ArPi Lab: A Low-cost Remote Laboratory for Control Education. *Preprints of the 19th World Congress*, The International Federation of Automatic Control Cape Town, South Africa.
- Prada, Miguel A., Fuertes, Juan J., Alonso, S., García, S., & Domínguez M. (2015). Challenges and solutions in remote laboratories. Application to a remote laboratory of an electro-pneumatic classification cell. *Computers & Education*, 85, 180-190.